

DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH-SPEAKING SKILLS OF MEDICAL ACADEMIC LYCEUM STUDENTS THROUGH INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Abstract: The use of interactive teaching methods has a positive effect on the development of speaking skills in a foreign language, in particular in English. The authors described modern forms, principles and methods of organizing interactive teaching of communication skills in English to medical students. This article examines the main methods of interactive teaching of speaking skills. The authors identified the strengths and weaknesses, from their point of view, in the use of interactive methods of teaching students speaking skills. It was noted that interactive classes not only contribute to improving the level of students' knowledge of English, but also develop their ability to work both independently and in a team, with a non-standard approach to solving problems. We identified the optimal interactive technologies for teaching medical students monologue and dialogic speech through interactive technologies: cooperative learning technologies, collective-group learning technologies, discussion technologies and modeling. Cooperative learning technologies used in English classes involve working in small groups and using the Carousel method. These technologies can be used in study groups with different levels of English language knowledge.

Keywords

interactive learning, monologue and dialogic speaking, medical students, professional English, innovation, improving academic performance.

Introduction

Modern requirements for the knowledge and skills of specialists in Russia determine the need for significant changes in the higher education system. In contrast to the traditional requirements for the professional competence of a

specialist, which imply mastering certain theoretical knowledge and practical skills of professional activity, a significant place in the new educational and qualification characteristics is occupied by the ability to creatively solve a problem, unconventional thinking, teamwork skills, etc.

Researchers note that today the learning process in a higher educational institution require certain transformations, in particular the intensive use of the method of interactive interaction of a student with the educational environment. We consider it appropriate to explore possible methods aimed at improving the interactive teaching of medical students in English language.

Materials and research methods

The purpose of the article is to substantiate the need to introduce interactive teaching of speaking in English to medical students, to determine the principles of such teaching, to classify the main methods of interactive teaching and to highlight the best ones, to conduct a qualitative analysis of the effectiveness of teaching using the interactive method.

Results and discussion

Analysis of the latest research and publications. A number of domestic scientists have devoted their research to the study of interactive technologies for teaching English: Norboeva (Norboeva,2020), Selivanov (Selivanov, 2015), Zimnyaya (Zimnyaya, 1999), etc. For example, the Soviet didactician Golant Ya. in the 60s of the 20th century formulated an active learning model as the interaction of a teacher and a student, and thus described the essence of interactive learning (Golant, 1969). The famous educator and engineer Rivin A. back in 1911. proposed a technology of teaching in pairs, which, in turn, laid the foundation for the method of group work of interactive learning.

The use of interactive learning in teaching English in higher education has been studied by many scientists: Rolgaiser (Rolgaiser, 2016), Shanskaya (Shanskaya, 2021), Dobrynina (Dobrynina, 2010), etc.

The topic of interactive teaching of English in universities is the subject of numerous scientific and methodological conferences, which are held annually by various universities. The authors perceive the use of interactive learning in different ways, but what they have in common is that the interactivity of learning and equal interaction between teacher and student constitute the world standard of higher education.

The process of teaching a foreign language, in particular teaching students communication skills in a foreign language, should, in our opinion, take place using interactive techniques. Interaction in speaking necessitates the use of interactive technologies as a method that directly facilitates learning interaction. Interactive technologies also contribute to the development of the ability to think outside the box and solve new problems.

Within the scope of the need for future doctors to master a foreign language, interactivity of learning contributes to the development of communication skills in a foreign language with patients, colleagues, information exchange and the search for non-standard solutions in English-language sources.

Interactive teaching of medical students of monologue and dialogic speech in English occurs using direct and indirect learning strategies. Direct strategies of interactive learning include memorization, cognition, and compensatory strategies (overcoming difficulties, solving problems). Indirect strategies include goal-cognitive strategies (defining the essence of the subject of language), emotional strategies (ability to self-control) and communicative-social (communicative attitude, compliance with the rules of etiquette and professional behavior). That is, interactive learning not only promotes the development of certain knowledge in the field of English, but also promotes the development of skills and abilities of direct interaction in this language.

The aim of interactive teaching of English language communication skills to medical students is to create comfortable learning conditions that encourage

students to interactive excellence: improving their English language communication skills on professional topics.

Collective group learning technologies include technologies such as: "Microphone",

"Openwork Saw", "Snow Avalanche". These technologies can be used to work with students who have a low initial level of knowledge, in order to develop their speaking skills.

Modeling technologies include role-playing business games, which are especially relevant for medical students, for example, when considering cases. In our opinion, these technologies are desirable to use in working with students whose level of knowledge is not lower than intermediate.

Discussion as an interactive method of teaching foreign language speaking includes various techniques: debates, round tables, brainstorming, press conferences, etc. These technologies require a high level of knowledge from students, since their lack of grammatical and lexical base will prevent them from correctly formulating statements at the text level.

You can also use interactive technical methods when teaching students: working with a video projector, video clips, working on the Internet, completing electronic homework on Skype, etc. Creating your own group on Facebook or Twitter helps to activate students' cognitive activity and improve learning outcomes. The following types of work can be used in English classes:

- prompts with pictures (a picture of a medical condition or organ that they must describe or discuss);
- an assignment to develop thinking skills (the teacher asks students questions on treatment issues and gives time for discussion in a small group, then the students express their own thoughts);
- choral work (the teacher asks a question and can assess the level of preparedness of the group based on the level of participation of the group when answering in

- chorus); - "free lines" - before studying the topic, students are offered a text with missing spaces for sentences, which they must fill in in the group after studying;
- physical response - students are asked to show with gestures their agreement or disagreement with the teacher's statements, after which they must confirm it orally;
 - self-assessment of their own learning by students and - at the end of studying the topic, each student must identify in English his or her weaknesses and strengths and indicate what he or she does not know well enough;
 - "phrase without words" - the teacher offers students a phrase describing a phenomenon on the topic being studied, but this phrase is missing one word, which the group must determine;
 - ethical dilemmas - the teacher describes specific medical ethical dilemmas that students must solve or present their own vision;
 - "polarity" - the teacher provides students with two opposing points of view on a certain medical phenomenon, students must determine the correct solution;
 - "riddles and guesses" - the teacher formulates a problem, the solution to which the students must guess, in a group;
 - "personal tasks" - involving each student in cooperation, when the teacher gives tasks that directly concern each student, for example, to find a patient with a certain disease among acquaintances and talk about their own experience of treatment or diagnosis;
 - focusing - defining several main ideas that students can master while studying the topic, discussing these ideas with students.

The conducted analysis of the literature allowed us to determine the main principles of interactive teaching English to students (in particular medical students):

- constant interaction between the teacher and students, as well as between students;

As for group work in English lessons, we consider it appropriate to use the following methods:

- the puzzle method - groups of students exchange participants who have mastered certain information, and together they must make a common presentation on a certain topic;
- rotation between groups - a constant exchange of group representatives during the work process;
- "layered pie" - discussing a problem in a group, changing participants, discussing a new problem, changing participants again, and returning to the original question;
- "three roles" - dividing students into three categories - those who ask a question, those who disagree, and those who support the point of view, and students must change groups all the time;
- "film club" - discussing films dedicated to a certain medical phenomenon, proposing their own script for such a film;
- associations - students must define or demonstrate a phenomenon, others guess;
- "blender" - students offer their own ideas on a given question, two people start the work, a third one joins them, whose idea is in tune with the proposed one, and then others join in, whose ideas are logically connected.

Conclusion

Conclusions and prospects for further research. The use of interactive methods in teaching medical students English is a necessary component of activating students' cognitive activity and improving academic performance.

The introduction of interactive learning is possible if the following principles are met: the principle of systematicity, clear organization of the educational process. Direct strategies of interactive learning include memorization, cognition, and compensatory strategies. Indirect strategies include cognitive strategies, emotional and communicative-social strategies. The goal of interactive teaching medical students English speaking skills is to create comfortable learning conditions that encourage students to interactive improvement: improving their communication skills in English on professional topics.

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